

THERMOMECHANICAL PROCESSING OF IN SITU Al-Cu/TiC/Al₂O₃ COMPOSITE

S.-H. Kim^{*}, J.-M. Lee, J.J. Kim, D.-K. Kim, H.J. Kim, Y.H. Kim
Structural Materials Division, Korea Institute of Materials Science,
531 Changwondaero, Changwon, Gyeongnam, Republic of Korea

^{*} Corresponding author (shawnkim@kims.re.kr)

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1. Introduction

Aluminum matrix composites having low densities, high specific strengths, and high stiffness are promising materials for transportation applications. Metal matrix composites (MMC) can be fabricated by ex situ or in situ processes. In ex situ processing, the reinforcements are prepared separately and added to the matrix. Ex situ MMCs often exhibit poor wettability between the reinforcements and the matrix. In situ processing, in which the reinforcements are synthesized in a matrix by a chemical reaction, is an effective method for producing particle-reinforced metal alloys having good interfacial properties between the particles and matrix [1]. Several in situ fabrication processes of MMCs have been suggested [2-11], and aluminum matrix composites can be fabricated by in situ casting processes.

Recently, heat-treatable aluminum alloy matrix composites have received much attention. Thermochemical processing can be used to tailor their microstructure and aging response [12-14] and thereby provide them with enhanced mechanical properties. Combinations of particle reinforcement and precipitation hardening can also provide improved properties of composite materials.

The present study focuses on the effect of thermomechanical processing on microstructure evolution and mechanical properties of an in situ Al-Cu/TiC/Al₂O₃ composite. Deformation behavior of the composite and the distribution of the reinforced particles were studied. The effects of the thermomechanical processing conditions on the aging characteristics are also discussed.

2. Experimental

The material used in this study was an Al-Cu alloy matrix composite, reinforced with TiC and Al₂O₃ particles, fabricated by an in situ casting process. Table 1 shows the chemical composition of the materials measured by inductively coupled plasma (ICP) analysis. The high concentration of Ti may be due to the presence of TiC particles. Cu, Si, and Mg could be present in the form of solidified phases or as solutes in the matrix. X-ray diffraction analysis of the as-cast material was carried out using Cu-K α radiation.

Figure 1 shows the thermomechanical processing schedule of the material. The as-cast rectangular specimen was solution-treated at 525°C for 18 h in an air atmosphere and subsequently quenched in water. The solution-treated specimen was heated to 525°C again and hot rolled to reduce the thickness by 30%. The hot-rolled strip was then cold-rolled to further reduce the thickness, by 80%, and provide the final 4mm thickness. The cold-rolled strip was annealed, aged, or re-solutionized and aged. Annealing was carried out at 400°C for 15 h in an air atmosphere. For the aging treatment, a specimen of the cold-rolled strip was immersed in an oil bath at 160°C for 28 h. Another specimen of the cold-rolled strip was re-solutionized by heating at 500°C for 2 h and then aging at 160°C. Electrical conductivity of the specimens was measured using an eddy current-type conductivity meter to monitor solutionizing or aging behaviors.

Table 1. Chemical composition (wt%) of as-cast Al-Cu/TiC/Al₂O₃ composite measured by ICP analysis.

Cu	Si	Mg	Ti	Al
5.28	0.60	0.67	2.66	Bal.

Fig. 1. Thermomechanical processing of Al-Cu/TiC/Al₂O₃ composite.

The microstructure of the specimens was observed using optical and scanning electron microscopy (SEM). Longitudinal sections of the specimens were polished mechanically and subsequently etched in a 0.5% hydrofluoric acid solution. Micro-Vickers hardness was also measured under the condition of 100 g applied force for 10 s.

3. Results and Discussion

Figure 2 shows the optical microstructure of the as-cast material. Small globular reinforced particles were dispersed in the matrix, and large angular particles were occasionally observed. X-ray diffraction identified TiC and Al₂Cu (θ phase; Fig. 3). The dispersed particles observed in Figure 2 are mostly TiC reinforcement. Al₂Cu phase can be formed during solidification of the Al-Cu matrix. Al₂O₃ (α phase) was not found by X-ray diffraction, possibly because of the small volume fraction. Al₂O₃ reinforcements were identified by energy dispersive spectroscopy (EDS) analysis. Figure 4 shows that the small globular particles and large angular particles are TiC and Al₂O₃, respectively.

Fig. 2. Optical micrograph of as-cast Al-Cu/TiC/Al₂O₃ composite.

Fig. 3. X-ray diffraction pattern of as-cast Al-Cu/TiC/Al₂O₃ composite.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 4. SEM micrographs and EDS analysis of reinforcements of cold rolled Al-Cu/TiC/Al₂O₃ composite. (a) TiC and (b) Al₂O₃.

Table 2 shows the mean sizes and the volume fractions of the reinforced particles measured by image analysis of optical micrographs of an as-cast specimen. The volume fractions of TiC and Al₂O₃ were 2.8 and 0.16, respectively.

Figure 5 shows the particle distribution after cold rolling. Small TiC particles were aligned along the rolling direction. Figure 6 shows a fractured coarse Al₂O₃ particle in the cold-rolled specimen. The incompatibility between a deforming matrix and non-deformable particles can cause breakage of the Al₂O₃ reinforcements. Geometrically-necessary dislocations can also allow compatible deformation of the two phases [15]. The presence of the reinforcements can be both beneficial and harmful to the mechanical properties of the material. Generation of additional dislocations can increase the strength of the material, but crack formation around the particles can diminish the ductility of the material.

Table 2. Quantitative analysis of reinforcements of as-cast Al-Cu/TiC/Al₂O₃ composite.

Reinforcement	Mean size (μm)	Volume fraction (%)
TiC	1.4	2.8
Al ₂ O ₃	22	0.16

Fig. 5. TiC particle distribution in longitudinal section SEM micrograph of cold-rolled Al-Cu/TiC/Al₂O₃ composite.

Fig. 6. Fractured Al₂O₃ particles in longitudinal section SEM micrograph of cold rolled Al-Cu/TiC/Al₂O₃ composite.

Figure 7 shows the electrical conductivities of the thermomechanically processed specimens. No changes after the solution treatment indicates that the matrix of the as-cast material was already supersaturated by the solute elements. Interestingly, the conductivity was increased by hot and cold rolling. Because hot rolling is carried out at elevated temperature, precipitation can occur during heating or hot rolling, resulting in an increase in the conductivity of the matrix. Rolling can also remove voids formed by the casting process and thereby increase the conductivity. The densities of the specimens were measured to examine the changes in void fraction. The densities of the solutionized, cold rolled and hot rolled specimens were 2.808, 2.821, and 2.822 g/cm³, respectively. Thus, the influence of cold rolling on density change was negligible. Another possibility for the increase in conductivity by cold rolling is deformation-induced precipitation, as reported elsewhere [12], although the role of particle reinforcement on precipitation behavior remains controversial. The increase in electrical conductivity by annealing or aging treatments is due to precipitation. The re-solutionizing treatment decreased the electrical conductivity.

Figure 8 shows the micro-Vickers hardness of the thermomechanically processed specimens. The highest hardness was obtained by re-solutionizing and subsequent aging. The high hardness of solutionized specimens may be due to natural aging. Annealing can recrystallize the matrix and thereby decrease the hardness.

Fig. 7. Electrical conductivity of thermomechanically processed Al-Cu/TiC/Al₂O₃ composite.

Fig. 8. Micro-Vickers hardness of thermomechanically processed Al-Cu/TiC/Al₂O₃ composite.

Figure 9 shows precipitates of the thermomechanically processed specimens observed under SEM. Small globular and plate-like precipitates were found in both the cold-rolled specimen and the aged specimen. The precipitates in the cold-rolled specimen may have been formed during hot rolling or cold rolling. Because the precipitates were already formed in the cold-rolled state, aging of the cold specimen did not increase the hardness (Fig. 7). Precipitates were not found in the re-solutionized specimen. The re-solutionizing treatment can increase aging hardenability so that the re-solutionized and aged specimen exhibited the highest hardness.

Fig. 9. SEM micrographs of Al-Cu/TiC/Al₂O₃ composite; (a) cold-rolled, (b) aged for 15 h, and (c) re-solutionized.

4. Conclusions

For in situ-fabricated Al-Cu/TiC/Al₂O₃ composites that were thermomechanically processed:

Rolling caused small globular TiC particles to be re-distributed and aligned along the rolling direction, and fractured coarse Al₂O₃ particles.

The measured increase in hardness after hot and cold rolling could be attributed to deformation-induced precipitation.

The re-solutionized and aged specimen exhibited the highest hardness among specimens processed in different ways.

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